

Expectation from YouTube Data Exports

Dear participant,

This survey seeks to understand what insights you expect to gain when accessing your personal data through GDPR data exports on YouTube. Under the GDPR, Article 15, you have the right to request and download a copy of your personal data from various platforms, which includes the information they collect about you.

This survey is being conducted jointly by academic researchers from XYZ. Your valuable opinion expressed in this survey may contribute to important research findings. So, we request you to read the instructions carefully and answer all the questions judiciously.

Results from the survey may be published in a research forum. The insights will be published in aggregate forms (such as averages and/or totals). We will neither publish nor share any information which can disclose any of your confidential information. All information will be protected to the greatest extent allowed by law, and data will be kept secured during and after the survey.

🚫⚠️ Please do not use ChatGPT or any other large language models (LLMs) to generate your responses. We are specifically seeking your personal thoughts. If we determine that your responses are AI-generated, you may not be eligible for compensation. ⚠️🚫

Selecting the "Agree" button indicates the following:

1. You have read the above information.
2. You voluntarily agree to participate in the "Expectation from YouTube Data Exports" survey.

* Indicates required question

1. I consent; begin the survey. *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

2. Please enter your Prolific ID here *

Background on GDPR Chapter 3: Rights of the Data Subjects

Under the GDPR Chapter 3 (Article 15), users have the right to request and download a copy of their personal data from various platforms, which includes the information they collect about you.

Let's take YouTube for an example. If you have been using YouTube video platform, you can go and request your data on the YouTube App and get a snippet of your data.

For the process of how to request your data and how a standard YouTube data looks like please refer to the information at this given url: [here](#)

3. Before taking this survey, were you aware of having such rights to access your personal data gathered by different online platforms? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

4. If yes, how did you know about these rights? *

Insights you expect from the YouTube Data - Browsing history

From here, we show different types of personal data like your browsing history, likes, etc. that you could see in your data exports upon request. We want to know what questions or insights about your activities would you be curious to know or understand from your data.

YouTube shares your recent **browsing history** with you in the following format (each entry contains only the fields shown below), what kind of insights would you be curious to know or understand from this data?

Browsing history or Watch history

Header : YouTube
Title : Watched [video title](#)
Author : [channel name](#)
Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51AM CET

Products : [YouTube]

Why is this here? : This activity was saved to your account because the following settings were on : YouTube watch history. You can control these settings [here](#).

5. Question - 1 *

6. Question - 2

7. Question - 3

Insights you expect from the YouTube Data - Search history

YouTube shares your recent **search history** with you in the following format (each entry contains only the fields shown below), what kind of insights would you be curious to know or understand from this data?

Search history

Header : YouTube
Title : Searched for [how to build pc](#)
Time : Oct 14, 2024 1:51AM CET

Products : [YouTube]

Why is this here? : This activity was saved to your account because the following settings were on : YouTube search history. You can control these settings [here](#).

8. Question - 1 *

9. Question - 2

10. Question - 3

Insights you expect from the YouTube Data - Comments

YouTube shares your **comments** with you in the following format (each entry contains only the fields shown below), what kind of insights would you be curious to know or understand from this data?

Comments

```
Comment ID : commentid_id_1
Channel ID : channel_id_1
Comment Create Timestamp : Aug 29, 2024, 9:18 AM
Price : 0
Parent Comment ID :
Video ID : video_id_1
Comment Text : {"text": "Such an amazing video! Made my day 😊"}"
```

11. Question - 1 *

12. Question - 2

13. Question - 3

Insights you expect from the YouTube Data - Watch later videos

YouTube shares your **watch-later videos** with you in the following format (each entry contains only the fields shown below), what kind of insights would you be curious to know or understand from this data?

Watch-later videos

Video ID : 9hD7q2CqAOA
Playlist Video Creation Timestamp : Aug 29, 2024, 9:18 AM

14. Question - 1 *

15. Question - 2

16. Question - 3

Insights you expect from the YouTube Data - Subscriptions

YouTube shares your **subscriptions** with you in the following format (each entry contains only the fields shown below), what kind of insights would you be curious to know or understand from this data?

Subscriptions

```
Channel Id : UC-LPIU24bQXVIjUXivKEeRQ  
Channel Url : http://www.youtube.com/channel/UC-LPIU24bQXVIjUXivKEeRQ  
Channel Title : Star plus
```

17. Question - 1 *

18. Question - 2 *

19. Question - 3

Summary & Self-Assessment

In this section, please reflect on how well you think you can understand and interpret your data on your own.

20. Would you like to gain any other insights from your YouTube data?

*Please write each insight / question with a line break. As shown below:
What websites did I visit the most?*

When did I last visit a site?

21. Have you ever requested your personal data from YouTube? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No Skip to question 25

Summary & Self-Assessment (Continuation)

In this section, please reflect on how well you think you can understand and interpret your data on your own.

22. What was the reason for requesting data from YouTube? *

23. Roughly, what percentage of questions that you mentioned during the survey were you able to infer from your data? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

0% (100% (All))

24. How confident are you that you can find the answers to your questions from the data on your own? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not Very confident

About you

In this section, you will be asked a series of questions about yourself. None of these sensitive details will be shared in a way which will jeopardize your privacy.

25. You describe yourself as *

Mark only one oval.

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say
- Other: _____

26. Age (in years) *

Mark only one oval.

- 18-25
- 25-30
- 30-40
- 40+

27. Which of the platforms do you use? *

Check all that apply.

- Facebook
- Instagram
- Tiktok
- Youtube
- LinkedIn
- Snapchat
- Twitter

28. Occupation *

Google Forms